

Connection of Tourism with International Relations

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Abstract: Huge improvement of tourism can be seen as a good source of exchanging currency among countries as well as it leads altering possible knowledge between west and east countries and it may be a clear reason to open small but not least facts about connecting tourism in terms of recreational field with international relations. In turn, exchanging currency will affect to GDP.

Key points: GDP, recreational field, huge improvement, diplomatic relations, heritage, tourism, currency.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking about tourism always goes to exchanging money and keeping alive history. But there is an important term which leads diplomatic relations. Through tourism, diplomatic relations are connecting, even nowadays appearing. Thanks to wave of tourists countries are made contracts that lead friendship among countries and tourism makes a bridge among especially recreational tourism.

MAIN BODY

Undoubtedly, tourism has been increasing dramatically for last years and in turn, it leads to make improvement of other sections such as diplomatic relations of countries, saving cultural and historical heritages. In fact the meaning of tourism might be like as bridge into many countries first and foremost it creates many doors to open history and historical culture in each single country as well as it gives opportunity to keep one's heritage to new generations. On the other hand, tourism does not demand hard-working in order to keep being international acknowledged of history.

Thanks to have relax and being refreshed tourists can take certain type of knowledge and experience about one object of country. However, there is a few places like Bahamas in where tourists may just chill out and take inner peace. It also helps changing currencies and increasing mind of national residents towards tourists.¹

Every day, international issues are in the news headlines – this is your chance to become an expert on relations between states, economies, ideas and societies. In a world where nuclear weapons remain primed for use, the world economy teeters on the brink of collapse and delicate ecosystems

¹ Adkhamovich, A. S., & Jaxongirovna, A. N. (2023). Features of Innovative Development of the Market of Tourist Services in Uzbekistan. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(4), 32-35.

are under threat, it is little wonder that our International Relations degree is proving a popular choice among students who wish to better understand the world's most challenging problems.

International Relations is a multidisciplinary subject, which draws in contributions from politics, history, media, sociology, law, economics and religion. Global issues dominate the news headlines on a daily basis and International Relations will allow you to focus on this dimension of politics. This is an opportunity to become an expert in international issues in a historical, political and cultural context.²

All our academics are conducting internationally published research. Our key strengths are in Theories of International Relations; Peace and Conflict; British and US foreign policy and EU and UN politics. Our subject deals squarely with some of the most daunting, intractable but important challenges of today.³

As more people struck out on adventures abroad and afar, international relations became an even more integral part of tourism and daily life than it had before. The debates and documentation surrounding this issue can clearly be seen in the government documents and brochures that are held in *Leisure, Travel & Mass Culture: The History of Tourism*, as well as in the individual accounts of holidaymakers and advice from travel agents.⁴

Even in the early days of organised mass travel, the potential of travel agents, with their knowledge of foreign climes, was recognised and harnessed by government agencies. In 1884, John Mason Cook of Thomas Cook and Son was asked to assist in the attempt to retrieve General Gordon from his precarious situation in rebellious Khartoum (and advertised the opportunity to his customers in the Thomas Cook periodical *Excursionist Home and Foreign Tourist Advertiser, American Edition, Series 34, Number 9*). He also later went on to arrange a tour of Palestine for Kaiser Wilhelm II in 1898, though he unfortunately died of dysentery during his efforts. These events show that the relationship fostered between tourist agencies and the foreign countries they visited were being recognised and tourism itself was beginning to be seen as an important tool in international relations.

² Suyunovich, T. I., & Jaxongirovna, A. N. (2023). THE DIFFERENT WAYS OF USING ADVANCED GIS SYSTEM IN TOURISM FIELD AND EXPRESS THE HIGHER BENEFITS OF GIS AS COMPARED TO OTHER FIELDS. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*, 2(3), 42-45.

³ Suyunovich, T. I., & Jaxongirovna, A. N. (2023). WHY WE NEED A TOURISM AND THE POSSIBILITIES OF REMAINING IMPROVED TOURISM CONSTANTLY. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(7), 393-398.

⁴ Suyunovich, T. I., & Jaxongirovna, A. N. (2023). THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE WORLD, A COMPARISON OF ASIAN AND EUROPEAN TOURISM SERVICES AND AN EXAMINATION OF CERTAIN TOURISM PROBLEMS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 18, 61-64.

Economic Importance of tourism for OSPAR Contracting Parties:

Country/Region	Km of coastline	GVA	Employment	Year(s) of reference	Reference
Belgium	98	€ 335,814 million €	27,000 FTE	2007, 2013	Belgische Staat, 2018
Denmark	4.605 (Baltic and North Sea)	DKK 16,491 (Approx. € 2,215)	32,537 FTE	-	Nielsen, Zhang, & Javakhishvili-Larsen, 2019
Ireland	4.577	€ 558 million	16,000 FTE	2018	Hynes, Aymelek, Corless, & Evers, 2018
UK	17.381	Approx. £4,5 billion (€ 5,49 billion)	Approx. 200 000	2016, 2012	Coastal Communities Fund, 2016; Beatty, Fothergill, & Gore, 2014
Portugal	1.187	1,660	45,950	2010-2013	INE, 2016
Netherlands	1.275	€ 2,654 million	30,000 FTE	2010, 2014	Statistics Netherlands, 2016
Norway	28.953 (without islands)	NOK 45,4 billion (€ 4,88 billion)	88,400	2016	Statistics Norway
France: Eastern Channel North Sea Basin	1.022	N/A	23% of all coastal tourism jobs located here	2013	Direction interregionale de la Mer, 2019
France: North Atlantic Western Channel Sea Basin	2.700	N/A	40,458 jobs depending on coastal tourism	2012	Ministère de la Transition écologique et solidaire, 2019
France: South Atlantic Sea Basin	720	N/A	29,400 jobs in tourism (representing 60% of the maritime economy)	-	Direction interrégionale de la mer Sud-Atlantique, 2019

The statistics saying that tourism remains even nearly main income source.⁵

Of course, in terms of diplomatic relations are also can not be left without impact of tourism. In the context of globalization, tourism has become one of the important social, economic and cultural factors. Tourist are not just a source of exchanging currency or keeping history to generation. But also tourists are also a type of ambassadors among countries. The effectiveness of innovative activity is determined by the innovation infrastructure, which is the basic component of innovative economy, potential of society and it is able to bring the economy to a higher level. When a big number of tourists are coming into one country there appears good diplomatic relations and even appears . So tourism plays a role of bridge among countries. Even we can think about innovative

⁵ Novikov V.S. Innovations in tourism. Textbook // M, Academy Publishing Center, 2007, 208s.

ways of tourism. The main characteristics of the goals of innovation in tourism can be summarized as follows.⁶

The activities of the tourism organization are quite diverse, so it is necessary to identify key spaces within which, as necessary, the goals of innovation are established. Such spaces provide significant guidelines for action. In order to improve tourism system there are a lot of ways to make rapid development of the digital economy today and the development of advanced technologies in the near future, representing a new type of economic relations in all sectors of the world market, which can become the main form of money exchange around the world. That is totally connected tourism fields. As a result, tourism creates deep connection among nation through digital and innovative way.⁷

CONCLUSION

Improvement of tourism not only recreational but all types of it should be advanced due to possible progress of diplomatic relations of different countries. In the past, there was a lack of tourists and no one cared about advancing benefits with tourists but these days every single country understanding benefits of it especially when it comes to diplomatic relations.

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⁶ Ilyin E.N. and others. *Fundamentals of tourism activities.*- M.: Ros.international.academic.tourism, 2000.

⁷ Suyunovich, T. I., & Sobirov, B. (2021). Ways to increase the competitiveness of tourism services through the application of digital technologies in Uzbekistan. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 13.